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Accessibility to Domestic Energy among Rural Households: Case Study of Damboa Wagaram Ward of Damboa Local Government Area of Borno State, Nigeria

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to analyze the accessibility of rural household to fuelwood in Damboa Wagaram Ward of Borno State, Nigeria. Forty households were randomly selected from where respondents for the study were obtained. Data obtained from the study were analyzed by the use of descriptive statistics. The result showed that 97.5% of respondents used fuelwood solely or complimented with other sources of domestic energy like cow dung or corn stalk. The quantity of fuelwood consumed by respondent households was an average of 6.8Kg/household/ day and 1.1Kg/person/day. When determined in monetary terms, it was found to be an average consumption cost per household per day of ₦81 while the average cost per person per day was ₦13.5. Kerosene, which was more available than other substitutes of fuelwood as domestic energy had very low sole demand (2.5%). This was as a result of its cost (₦275/household/day), compared to that of fuelwood. It was recommended that more sustainable ways of consuming fuelwood should be encouraged. Furthermore, Other sources of domestic energy such as kerosene, liquefied natural gas and electricity will need to be introduced to rural women in order to reduce the rate of loss of the natural forest in the study area.

Key Words: Fuelwood, consumption, women, rural area.

INTRODUCTION

The exploitation of fuel wood by the inhabitants of any area is an inevitable consequence of human existence. This is because fuelwood is a vegetal resource which provides the main source of domestic fuel for both the rural and urban households (Ikurekong *et al.*, 2009). It has been estimated that about 50% of the world's population depend on fuelwood or other biomass fuel for cooking and other domestic uses, with a daily per capita consumption of about 0.5kg to 1.00kg of dry biomass (Twindel and Wier, 1986) and an average annual per capita consumption of 0.77m³, or 0.18 in Africa (WEC/FAO, 1999). In Nigeria, fuelwood and charcoal account for over 80% of national energy consumption (Foley, 1986).

Wood as a source of energy does not contribute to global warming. Although it emits carbon dioxide during combustion, wood is also a natural source of carbon dioxide absorption during forest growth. In view of increasing environmental concerns, wood could be a good substitute for polluting fossil fuels. Furthermore, the forestry sector (wood for energy) creates more jobs than the other energy sectors. According to the Bianco Report (1998), for the equivalent of one ton of fuel oil, fuelwood can create three times more jobs than fossil fuels (Couture *et al.*, 2011). The reckless exploitation, and in some cases, over exploitation of these resources however, have often resulted in environmental degradation (UNEP, 1991a; 1994; UNEP/ISRC, 1990; UNECA, 1992; Thomas and Middleton, 1973; SARDC, 1994).

The shortage of fuelwood has undermined both the health and well-being of households. It has also significantly altered the basis of life for the rural poor as other dangers of extensive biomass fuel use have been found to constitute a serious ecological threat. Added to this is the unaffordability of alternative energy sources induced by the exorbitant cost of stoves, cookers and utensils and cooking fuels such as kerosene, which manifests

in a crisis of energy accessibility that the fuelwood users are trapped in. This, as observed by Macaulay et al. (1989), represents a problem of social equity for the poor. This rate of rising exploitation of fuelwood calls for serious and urgent concern at the global, national and local levels, many of which must be based on the availability of facts and quantitative data which, in most cases, are generally lacking. The paper is an attempt to contribute to filling this gap. The study will determine the quantity and cost of fuelwood consumption compared to kerosene, the commonest non wood alternative domestic energy in Nigeria, in a bid to explain the massive consumption of fuelwood in rural areas. This study therefore had the major objective of investigating the accessibility to domestic energy among rural households. Case study of Damboa Wagaram ward of Damboa Local Government Area of Borno State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The Study Area

Damboa wugaram is a ward in Damboa Local Government Area (LGA) in Borno state, Nigeria. Damboa LGA shares border with kaga and konduga local government areas to the North, Yobe state in the North West, Biu LGA in the South West, Chibok LGA in the South, Gwoza LGA in the northwest and Adamawa state in the south-east. It covers a land area of about 6800km² with a population of 231,573, according to National Population Commission (census, 2006). It lies between longitude 12^o and 45^o East and latitude 11^o and 09^o North. Ninety (90) percent of people in the population are small- scale farmers and farming is the major occupation of the people in the area. The common sources of domestic energy in the area are fuelwood, charcoal and kerosene. The major tribes found in the area are Marghi, Chibok and other minority tribes such as Fulani, Hausa, Kanuri, Babur and Shuwa Arabs. (Hassan, 2008). The source of data for this study was primary data which involved the use of questionnaire as well as interview schedule for illiterate respondents. Weight balance was used to weigh fuelwood as required.

From Damboa wagaram ward, five units out of eight were randomly selected for the study and eight households were randomly selected from each of the selected units, giving a total sample size of forty respondent households from where 40 respondent women were obtained. The technique employed for data analysis was descriptive statistics including frequency tables, means, percentages, and standard deviation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Quantity and Cost of Fuelwood Consumed by Household

The quantity and costs of fuelwood consumed by households was studied to examine how quantity of fuelwood supplied varies with their respective prices and household size.

Table 1: Quantity and cost of Fuelwood Consumed in the Study Area per day

Price(₦/day)	Freq	Percentage	Mean (₦/day)	Std	Average cost (₦)
≤40	7	17.9	20	39.34	81.9/Household/day
41-80	7	17.9	60.5		
81-120	22	56.4	100.5		13.5/Person/day
121-160	1	2.6	140.5		4,927.5/Person/year
161-200	2	5.1	180.5		
	39	100			

Source: Field Survey, 2011.

The analysis of Table 1 revealed that majority of the respondents (56.4%) had a family size of 8-10 and spent about ₦81- 120 on fuelwood per day while household size of 12-15 spent ₦161- ₦200 per day. The average consumption price per household per day was ₦81 while the average price per person was ₦13.5. This implies that the higher the family size the higher will be the amount spent on fuelwood consumed per day. This further implies that an individual will spent ₦4, 927.5 annually.

Table 2: Distribution of Quantity of Fuelwood Consumed

Qty (Kg/day)	Percentage	Frequency	Mean	Std	Average consumption (Kg)
≤4	7.7	3	2	3.98	6.8 Kg/HH/day
4.1-8	84.6	33	6.05		1.1 Kg/person/day
8.1-12	7.7	3	20.1		401.5Kg/person/yr
	100	39			

Source: computed from field survey Data, 2011.

Table 2 showed that 84.6% of the respondents with household size of 6-9 persons consumed about 4.1-8 Kg of fuelwood per day, while household size of 10-15 persons consumed 8.1-12 Kg of fuelwood per day. Therefore, the average consumption of fuelwood per household per day was 6.6 Kg while the average consumption of fuelwood per person per day stood at 1.1 Kg. this implies that the average consumption of fuelwood per person per year will be 401.5 Kg.

Table 3: Distribution of Quantity of Kerosene Consumed

Quantity of kerosene (L)	Frequency	Mean	Average consumption (L)
2.5-3	1	2.75	2.75/HH/day 0.344/person/day 125.56/person/yr

Source: field Data, 2011.

Table3 showed kerosene as a sole source of domestic fuel with an average consumption of 275L/household/day while an individual consumed only 34.4L/day. This resulted in a consumption of 12,556L/year for each individual.

Table 4: Distribution of Price of Kerosene Consumed

Family size	Cost (₦)	Frequency	Mean	Average cost (₦)
S8	250-300	1	275	275/HH/day 34.4/Person/day 12,556/person/yr

Source: computed from field Data, 2011.

Table 4 showed that only one respondent used kerosene as a sole source of domestic fuel, when comparing table 1 with 4, it was found that the average amount spent on fuelwood per day per person (₦13.5) was less than that spent on kerosene per person per day (₦34.4). This implies that the respondents preferred to use fuelwood to kerosene because of the exorbitant high price and scarcity of kerosene in the area.

The Socio-economic Implication of Fuelwood Consumptions on the Environment.

The socio-economic implication of fuelwood on the environment was studied to investigate the implication of continuous consumption of fuelwood on the environment such as soil erosion, decreased availability of fuelwood as well as bush meat supply.

Table 5: Perceived Effect of Fuelwood Consumption on the Environment

Problems	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Scarcity of fuel wood now compared with before	16	43.2	1
Increasing soil erosion	10	27	2
Scarcity of bush meat	7	18.9	3
Shortage of fodder	4	10.8	4
Total	40	100	

Source: computed from field survey Data, 2011.

Ranks are in descending order of magnitude, no multiple responses existed hence, it is 100%.

The study revealed that the felling of trees for the provision of fuelwood is resulting in some perceived effect on the environment. Among these perceived observations of the respondents includes decreased availability of fuelwood (43%) resulting in increase of the distances covered to access the fuelwood. The implication of this is that there will be increase in the costs of fuelwood resulting from the greater cost involved in accessing it and its scarcity. The result also showed that 27% respondent observed increasing soil erosion in the area which is likely to be as a result of reduced tree cover causing the soil to be exposed to the vagaries of weather reducing soil productivity among farmers.

About 19% of the respondents also observed that the reduction of forest have resulted in scarcity of bush meat in the area since the animals have been deprived of their natural habitat. Others (almost 11%) observed that fodder for animals feed has become scarce due to a reduction of availability of forest resources. This has implications on access to animals feed as the environment may not be able to support livestock; fuelwood consumption in the study area (amounting to an average of over 400kg/person/year) is an important contributor to the depletion of forest and forest resources in the study area. This has serious consequences on the environment which results in deleterious implications for the inhabitants.

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